

Everyday Incivility and the Urban Interaction Order: Theorizing Moral Affordances in Ritualized Interaction

Mervyn Horgan, Department of Sociology & Anthropology, University of Guelph

Postal address:

Mackinnon 637, University of Guelph, 50 Stone Road East, Guelph, ON N1G2W1, Canada.

mhorgan@uoguelph.ca

Bio

Mervyn Horgan is associate professor in the Department of Sociology & Anthropology, University of Guelph and 2018/2019 Visiting Fellow at Yale University's Centre for Cultural Sociology. His core research interest is in the genesis and course of solidarity between strangers in everyday urban life, with special attention to the meanings that attach to both uncivil and convivial encounters.

Author accepted manuscript of:

Horgan, Mervyn, 2019. Everyday Incivility and the Urban Interaction Order: Theorizing Moral Affordances in Ritualized Interaction. *Journal of Language Aggression and Conflict* 7(1): 32–55. <https://doi.org/10.1075/jlac.00018.hor>

Everyday Incivility and the Urban Interaction Order: Theorizing Moral Affordances in Ritualized Interaction¹

Abstract

Treating uncivil encounters as breaches of the ritual contract of civil inattention (Goffman 1963), this article connects ritualized interaction between strangers in everyday life and the production and maintenance of moral order more generally. The ongoing enactment of the ritual of civil inattention maintains and characterizes the particular kind of moral order that strangers collectively produce in urban public spaces.

Drawing on select empirical materials—from unsolicited commentary to queue-jumping—gathered under the auspices of the Researching Incivility in Everyday Life (RIEL) Project this article builds upon the ‘everyday incivilities’ approach pioneered by Smith, Phillips and King (2010) to examine moral dimensions of everyday encounters between strangers. Preliminary analysis of the RIEL data indicates that ritual dimensions of interaction between strangers in public space provide interactants with *moral affordances*, that is, opportunities to align themselves with an idealized moral order through projective moral action.

Key terms: moral order; interaction ritual; strangers; affordances

1. Introduction

When strangers encounter one another in public space they usually ignore one another, but this is not always the case. For example, a woman and a man in their early twenties are sitting together on a public bus chatting about evolution. The woman recounts:

“after a while of talking about this, this guy just kind of butted in.....He acted like he was aggravated and was pretty rude about it...and was kind of aggressive I was kind of offended in how he reacted to the situation” (RIEL 17033).

This account of an everyday incivility between strangers was gathered through interviews conducted in a North American city between 2014 and 2018 as part of the Researching Incivility in Everyday Life (RIEL) Project.² The RIEL data comprises over 300 accounts of participants’ most recent encounter with a rude stranger in a public place. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 72. Two-thirds of participants identified as female, one-third as male, while roughly four-fifths identified as White/Caucasian, and about one-fifth

¹ Many thanks to the editors, anonymous reviewers, and to members of the Canadian Network for Critical Sociology for their valuable feedback. Jordan Daniels and Katie Zimmer provided outstanding research assistance. This paper is dedicated to the memory of Roy Turner (1928-2017). Roy’s thoughtful engagement with sociologies of the mundane and ordinary language philosophy, and his openly skeptical stance towards ethnomethodology taught me how the ethics and the analysis of ordinary encounters are

² Funded by a Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council Insight Development Grant (#430-2012-0833).

identified as members of visible minorities. In addition to demographic data, interviewers solicited a range of additional information on the spatio-temporal setting of the encounter, and asked more open questions regarding participants' feelings about and interpretations of the encounter, and their thoughts on incivility in general. In the account above, two young adults chatting on a public bus are intervened upon by a stranger acting in an aggressive manner.

As Goffman famously noted of Anglo-American society, in dense urban public places like buses, sidewalks, and parks, strangers generally provide one another with *civil inattention* (Goffman 1963, 83-88), an implicit contract whereby strangers agree not to afford one another undue attention. This does not mean that strangers completely ignore and disregard one another entirely, but rather that they provide one another with 'just-enough' attention to demonstrate that they do not constitute a threat. Goffman (1963, 84) describes civil inattention as "the slightest of interpersonal rituals". Civil inattention is preserved for strangers in particular, making it a curious kind of ritual, that, as Goffman (1963, 84) notes, "constantly regulates" interaction between strangers in public spaces. Where there is ritual, there is something sacred around which ritual is organized (Durkheim 1995). Large-scale formal rituals such as religious rites are organized around sacred texts and are oriented to gods, national rituals can be organized around flags and the 'glorious dead', but not all rituals make reference to some transcendental power, nor do they explicitly carry such gravity or involve large collectives.

As with interaction rituals in general, the ritual of civil inattention is organized around mutual recognition of the sacred character of face (Goffman 1967).³ When we encounter one another as strangers, A provides civil inattention to B and B provides it to A. Thus, relationality, however thin, rather than individual level action, is key (Ohashi & Chang 2017). Similarly, attention to context is essential (Culpeper 2010). It is useful here to think for a moment about contexts where civil inattention is *inappropriate*. To be inattentive to an intimate or friend is clearly an affront; it is generally considered rude to willfully ignore one with whom we are on friendly terms (for an astute early treatment of snubs amongst persons familiar to one another, see Turner 1970). But, when amongst strangers in high-use public spaces, strangers both expect and provide civil inattention. A clear exception here is *civil attention*, like responding to requests for assistance (see Kendrick & Drew 2016), but the data reported in this paper focuses on the shift from *civil inattention* to what we might call *uncivil attention*. In line with Goffman's formulation of the interaction order of Anglo-American urban public space, there is a generalized expectation that the *right* to civil inattention be upheld and generalized across spaces of strangership (Horgan 2012), that is, spaces where the most frequently occurring type of encounter is between strangers. Breaches of the ritual of civil inattention—variously called impoliteness, incivility, rudeness, or situational impropriety—constitute affronts to

³ As will become clear below, I disagree with the claim that Goffman's conception of ritual is too narrow (Kádár and Bax 2013; see also Wuthnow 1989). If anything, we have not yet fully explored the analytic possibilities that Goffman's work on ritual opens up.

the sanctity of individual face.⁴ If civil inattention is oriented to the sanctity of the individual, then ritual rupture is akin to profanation.

The mutually oriented character of the ritual of civil inattention forms the core of this article. This ritual is so frequent and ubiquitous that it goes largely unnoticed, but its apparent mundanity belies the depth of its moral character. Ritual ingredients structure possibilities for moral action, that is, the existence of an accepted and regularized ritual form of interaction provides a frame for both acting morally in the presence of others, and for interpreting the conduct of others as being in line with the contextually relevant moral order. In the case of copresent strangers, moral action involves granting civil inattention, a ritual that is repeated between physically copresent strangers daily. My suggestion is that civil inattention enacts everyday morality, which I take to refer to “individuals’ sense of themselves as behaving in a socially and personally acceptable way, in conformance to societal values and norms they see as binding” (Dromi 2012, 852). Further, I suggest that the ritual structure of stranger encounters affords strangers opportunities for demonstrably moral conduct—what I call ‘moral affordances’.

Having set some general context for my argument, below I quickly review existing research on strangers and incivilities, both in pragmatics and in sociology. I will then offer a conceptual framing for thinking about uncivil encounters between strangers that connects mutual commitment and moral order by way of interaction ritual, before briefly outlining a theory of moral affordances. This theory arose from preliminary analysis of the RIEL data, where active bystander interventions in acts of language aggression are relatively rare. Intervention appeared more regularly in the conditional or projective, that is, reported by participants as what they ‘should’, ‘could’ or ‘ought to’ have done when faced with a rude stranger (see also Culpeper 2011). While the theory is speculative, it grows out of the Goffmanian empirical tradition of establishing close connections between situational improprieties and public order (Goffman 1963, 1971). Finally, I will conclude by offering some thoughts on what the sociologically informed perspective outlined here might offer to pragmatics in general and to im/politeness studies in particular.

2. What we do and do not know about strangers and uncivil encounters

Sociologists and pragmatists alike take seriously seemingly unimportant interactions, viewing them as central to the production and reproduction of situated order and social structure. Mundane interactions between strangers provide ever more grist for our shared mill. Curiously, while the last decade has seen a burgeoning literature in pragmatics on impoliteness, very little research has been conducted on impolite interactions (1) between strangers and (2) in non-institutional settings. This is surprising given the conceptual fruits that may be harvested by taking seriously uncivil encounters between strangers in public space.

⁴ Though beyond the remit of this article, the connection between the sacred character of face and its need for ritual renewal is a clear way to connect social solidarity and moral order (Durkheim 1995; see also Bargiela-Chiappini 2003).

Shared understandings of the social world are central to everyday interaction. This rings true across a wide variety of analytic and generally commensurable perspectives, from social phenomenology (Schutz 1975), ethnomethodology (Garfinkel 1967), and interactional ritual theory (Collins 2005; Goffman 1967), to the geography of encounter (Valentine 2008; Jackson et al 2017) and plural subject theory (Gilbert 2014). For Schutz (1975), our lifeworld (*Lebenswelt*), our socially situated embodied experience of everyday life in the physical presence of other persons—‘consociates’—has a deep structure that depends on a range of shared background expectancies and common sense knowledge. These serve as a scheme of interpretation for responding to social situations. This resonates strongly with the pragmatic conception of ‘common ground’ and is foundational to the work of ethnomethodologists. For the most part, these background expectancies are sufficient for navigating mundane everyday life, but things can, and do, go awry.

2.1 Strangers and pragmatics: problems of common ground

Despite remarkable breadth and depth since the field’s origins (see, e.g., Bousfield 2008, 2010; Culpeper 1996; 2011), im/politeness research has yet to attend to im/politeness between physically copresent strangers in non-institutional settings. Moreover, with regard to impoliteness in particular, it is worth noting that among the (admittedly non-exhaustive) positive and negative impoliteness strategies sketched by Culpeper (1996, 357-358), very few can be applied to relations between strangers. That said, researchers have examined the role of phatic communication in facilitating interaction to generate basic ties and friendly relations between strangers (Blommaert and Varis 2015; Ide 1996). But, as noted, in im/politeness research and pragmatics more generally, encounters between physically copresent strangers are underscrutinized. Moreover, existing work dealing with interactions between strangers tends to be in the context of service delivery or institutionally proscribed interactions (e.g. classrooms, medical encounters). Similarly, conversation analysts have examined the uses of topical talk amongst unacquainted persons to generate conversation, though this work too tends to focus on talk in institutions (Maynard and Zimmerman 1984).

Analyzing interactions between strangers in large, dense, heterogeneous urban centres provides a limit case of sorts, where shared language cannot be assumed, and where ‘common ground’ (Clark 1992; Stalnaker 2002) is only of the most generalized sort. Stripping ‘common ground’ to its most basic and literal configuration—mere physical copresence, where all that may be common between strangers encountering one another is the shared business of using public space—is especially fruitful for advancing a general theory in im/politeness research. Indeed, encounters between strangers pose a particular challenge for im/politeness research, as those who do not share a common language may *interpret* one another as rude. That is, the absence of a shared language does not eliminate the possibility for some activity or utterance being interpreted as rude. This is especially pertinent in the context of large-scale complex multicultural societies where a shared language amongst strangers cannot be assumed. I will return to this point below.

2.2 Strangers and urban sociology: idealized sociability

While primarily considered an analyst of interaction in search of a generalizable grammar of social situations, much of Goffman's work is centrally concerned with urban sociability, and interactions between unacquainted persons in particular. He sought "to grasp some aspects of urban secular living" (Goffman 1967, 95) through "a version of urban ethnography" (Goffman & Verhoeven, 1980, 318). Indeed, the urban interaction order formed the analytic core of two of his major studies (1963; 1971). Drawing on Goffman to develop the everyday incivilities approach (discussed in more detail below), Smith et al. (2010, 14) focus on "the encounter as the atom of social life" since "coordinated action within the encounter" is central to "civil relations in public".

Many micro-oriented sociologists attend to the interactional organization of social life amongst strangers. For Lofland (1973, 151), densely populated urban public space is a "world of strangers" where urbanites develop a "symbolic shield of privacy" to deal with the intensity of sensory stimulation (Simmel 1971).⁵ Duneier and Molotch (1999, 1276) outline the "tacit conventions of sociability" that organize interactions between copresent strangers in urban space, while Anderson (2011) has proposed the "cosmopolitan canopy" as a concept for understanding spaces of civil sociability between strangers across socially salient categorical differences. More recently, Kaplan (2018) has suggested that strangers who share a general frame of reference can meet and engage in what he calls "social club sociability" based on affinities with collective representations unbounded by the constraints of the immediate interaction. While these conceptual innovations have much to recommend them, sociologists have barely scratched the surface in understanding uncivil encounters.

2.3 Interaction ritual and the social reproduction of moral order

Connections between ritualization and the maintenance of large-scale social order are quite clear (Turner 1995). For example, swearing in ceremonies for new national leaders generate and affirm commitments between individuals and nations. Marital rituals provide official recognition to bonds of intimacy and transform individuals into legally bound couples.⁶ While these rituals can generate controversies in the broader society, their symbolic function is clear. Less clear is the connection between mundane interaction ritual and the reproduction of moral order, though this is the subject of emerging lines of exciting research in sociology (Alexander et al. 2006; Collins 2005) and in pragmatics (Kádár 2017; Parvaresh and Tayebi 2018).

Moving between the relatively enclosed and conceptually discrete interaction ritual and the moral order is a more nebulous analytic terrain. Moral order has an ambiguous status across contemporary social science. While it is regularly invoked, there is little agreement

⁵ The classic sociological analysis of necessary emotional and interactional adaptations for navigating everyday urban life is Simmel's (1971) discussion of the 'blasé attitude'.

⁶ While the turn to ritual in pragmatics is relatively recent, some work has been done in multi-modal analyses of ritualized interaction, though this tends to focus on the interactional organization of *formal* ritual (see, for example, Hanks 2006).

on a clear operational definition (see, for example Hutchby and O'Reilly 2010; Jay 2018; Jayussi 1984; Kádár 2017). While moral order may appear to analysts as water to a fish, we can treat it as a 'sensitizing concept' (Blumer 1954) that refers to the stabilizing force of the diffuse obligation to abide by norms of conduct when in the presence of others. The normative demands that inhere in ritualized encounters have a moral force, and the persistent enactment of these norms makes for a stable and reproducible moral order. This is just as true for the weight of focused moral responsibility we may feel towards intimates, as it is for the more diffuse obligation to provide copresent strangers with civil inattention. Thus, interaction ritual provides a core mechanism for the reproduction of moral order (see Figure 1 below). The fact that social order is relatively stable and is ritually maintained implies that it is moral.

Despite their differences, theorists of social reproduction in sociology broadly agree that much of the work of structural reproduction occurs in the context of face-to-face interaction. This holds across theories that are otherwise irreconcilable, such as Archer's (1995) morphogenetic model, Bourdieu's (2000) field/habitus, Fine's (2014) idiocultures, and Giddens' (1986) structuration theory. On this view, human copresence—especially ritualized encounter—is a demonstrably necessary condition for structural reproduction. For these theorists of social reproduction, shifts in the moral order ought to be perceptible at the level of the encounter, and vice versa. More precisely, encounters and the moral order are in a recursive relation. For example, Walum (1974) shows how changing norms around sex roles in society are made manifest (and can create problems around interaction) in the organization of foot traffic through doors. This suggests that shifting patterns of deference in interaction simultaneously signal and generate shifts in moral order (see also Culpeper and Kádár 2010). The interaction order, then, is the realm of the moral, and ritualized encounters provide a cipher for accessing the interactional and interpretive topology of the moral order.

3. Mutual commitment and moral order

I was minding my own business, waiting in line on the platform for the subway when an impatient woman came through and just pushed past a bunch of people who were waiting to get on the train. She physically pushed me and another woman's child....during rush hour, so it was really packed once we got on, and she continued to push myself and other people to make room for herself. Lots of people were getting really irritated by her actions and giving her bothered looks (RIEL15041)

While enacted interactionally, civil inattention cannot be reduced to the immediate scene of interaction. In structural anthropology and cultural sociology, ritual is central to the production and maintenance of moral order (Durkheim 1995; Douglas 2005; Horgan 2014; Wuthnow 1989). While sociologists in general tend to favour the term 'social order', both ethnomethodologists and, more recently, pragmaticians tend towards the term 'moral order' (Kádár 2017, 28). Here, following Rawls' (2010) deep Durkheimianism, I treat social order as moral order, which in turn, echoes a consistent thread throughout Goffman's work, where individuals entering social situations enter also

a moral domain where they can expect to have moral rights and obligations requested and upheld (see, for example, 1959, 12-13). Queuing is the example *par excellence*. As the example above demonstrates, queues are easily breached. In urban North America, this most mundane activity involves mutual adherence to the ritual of civil inattention, while individuals implicitly negotiate a just means for distributing waiting time for accessing goods or services (Schwartz 1975). Thus breaches of the queue appear also to violate broader moral principles.

Every interaction order is a moral order. All interaction orders have as their basic organizing principle the moral commitment of those who collectively constitute and produce any given interaction order, a moral commitment both to one another, and to the order that being together produces (Goffman 1983; Rawls 1990). So, for example, bakers collectively produce the interaction order of the bakery through demonstrated commitment to one another *and* to the reproduction of the bakery. We could say the same for libraries and living rooms, carnivals and classrooms, bedrooms and boardrooms, public squares and private squabbles: interaction orders are not only populated, but are *constituted* and *organized* by the mutually oriented activities of those who are copresent. While every interaction order is a moral order, the question of how interaction orders are ‘loosely coupled’ (Goffman 1983a) to broader social structures remains an open one.⁷

Interaction orders call forth from copresent persons moral commitments that are specific to that interaction order and to the moral order of the broader society containing them. Similarly, the structure of the moral order is made evident in the character and course of mundane interactions: moral order is produced in the everyday doings and sayings of ordinary members. This is as true for bakeries, bedrooms and boardrooms as it is for the order collectively constituted by copresent strangers in urban public places, what may be called the *urban interaction order* (Horgan 2017a, 2017b).

Further, as products of copresence, all interaction orders are characterized by specifiable modes of face preservation (Brown and Levinson 1987). That said, as Bargiela-Chiappini (2003) demonstrates, early im/politeness studies contorted Goffman’s concept of face, filtered as they were through Brown and Levinson’s work. More recent im/politeness research develops a more fully Goffmanian conception of face (Garcés-Conejos Blitvich 2013; Locher & Watts 2005). In the context of the urban interaction order, face maintenance occurs through the ritual of civil inattention. Key to the argument presented here is that face is *ritually* preserved. Amongst strangers, face maintenance is deeply imbricated with moral order by way of the ritual of civil inattention. Worth restating here is that civil inattention does not mean ignoring the other in an absolute sense, but rather providing them with minimal recognition, sufficient to communicate mutual respect (Goffman 1963). If ordinary interaction orients to a moral order, then one of our primary tasks is to analyze the constitutive features of this order. Thus, our central concept is ritual rather than face.

⁷ In conversation analysis, Schegloff (1992) motions towards this possible synthesis. In pragmatics, studies of metapragmatic practices show some promise in delineating how extra-interactional features intervene in the structure of interaction (for examples in the case of heckling, see Kádár 2014; Kádár and Davies 2016).

Persons do not simply ‘populate’ an encounter. Encounters in general *constitute* a moral order; that is, moral order depends on the interactions occurring within it. The moral order upholds the moral worth of persons through ritualized reciprocity in interaction. Ritualized interaction expresses a mutual commitment amongst copresent persons and simultaneously constitutes the moral order. Thus, as a generic social process, interaction ritual is the means by which interacting individuals both produce and access the moral order: there is no individual level access to the moral order without going through interaction ritual (see Figure 1 below).

Individual <> Interaction Ritual <> Moral Order

Figure 1: Interaction ritual mediates the relationship between individual and moral order

3.1 Urban interaction order as moral order

Bringing this more explicitly to interactions between strangers; as noted earlier, strangers in urban public space offer one another civil inattention. That is, strangers do not ignore one another in an absolute sense, but rather demonstrate that they are *mutually* indifferent to one another.⁸ As Horgan (2012, 2017a; 2017b) demonstrates, the maintenance of the urban interaction order requires consistent offers of indifference, and in most urban encounters between strangers this offer is mutually honoured. Where Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between interaction ritual and moral order in general, Figure 2 shows how those who are strangers to one another uphold the urban interaction order through mutual adherence to the ritual of civil inattention.

Stranger <> Civil Inattention <> Urban Interaction Order
 (individual) (interaction ritual) (moral order)

Figure 2: The ritual of civil inattention upholds the urban interaction order

Since encounters between strangers have a ritual form, then there is always a possibility of ritual rupture. Mutuality, while central to interactions between strangers, is not a given. For this reason, encounters between strangers—in particular, those that go awry—are conceptually generative at underexplored intersections between pragmatics, sociology and psychology. In particular, incivilities between strangers provide a springboard for theorizing moral dimensions of everyday encounters. Attending to the organization of these encounters gets at that ‘loose coupling’ (Goffman 1983a) between the endogenous organization of interaction orders and the structuring force—both constraining and enabling—of more generalized moral order.

4. Accounting for accounts: from observed behaviours to interpreted experiences

⁸ Both Simmel (1971: 334) and Durkheim (1964: 298) use the term ‘mutual indifference’. This is distinct from what Horgan (2017a: 81-82) calls ‘non-mutual indifference’ which is characterized by interaction that lacks a mutuality of orientations, and that connects more readily to broader structural injustice.

I was at a [downtown] bar and the coat check lines there are usually pretty hectic ...this one girl had three jackets in her hand....just came from the back of the line and butted in front of everybody and everybody was giving her dirty looks...getting mad at her and...telling her to go to the back of the line and she just literally didn't even care and just walked right to the front (RIEL16041)

Compounding the complexity of analyzing uncivil encounters between copresent strangers is the problem of gathering appropriate data. Indeed, across im/politeness research what constitutes adequate or appropriate data remains an open question. This question is relatively straightforward in the case of on-line text-based interaction where trace evidence remains available for analysis (see, for example, Garces-Conejos Blitvich 2018; Parvaresh and Tayebi 2018). For analyzing interaction between physically copresent strangers the picture is somewhat more complicated. Indeed, by drawing data from artificial and contrived types of social settings such as “television ‘docusoaps’, or ‘fly- on-the-wall’ documentary serials” (Bousfield 2007, 2185), existing research on impoliteness stretches the bounds of what might be considered ‘naturally occurring’. Clearly the best data is naturally occurring (Hutchby 2008), but this is especially difficult in the context of incivilities between strangers.

One potential resolution to this methodological quandary is to treat incivilities as *interpreted* phenomena, that is, to treat an encounter as uncivil if any party in the interaction interprets it as uncivil. While this raises epistemological questions of its own, it does provide another means for accessing rich data—both qualitative and quantitative—on incivilities. This view of incivility as subjectively interpreted is a core element of the *everyday incivilities* perspective (Phillips and Smith 2003; Smith et al. 2010; Smith and King 2013). This works from the premise that unlike objects of natural scientific inquiry, uncivil encounters are *not objectively observable*, but are instead *subjectively interpreted*: rather than offender and victim, think offender and offended. If incivilities are interpreted, then their ontology depends on accounts, as accounts are intelligible interpretation's domain (Scott and Lyman 1968). Thus, the methodological strategy of the everyday incivilities perspective implicitly aligns in part with elements of second wave im/politeness research, though these confluences have yet to be explored.

On this view, moral order is not alone an *observed behavioural* product of social life—a mere aggregation of individual interactions—it is also an *interpreted experiential* one. Respondents' reporting of encounters must make themselves interpretable. That is, accounts are offerings of interpretable material: they are tellings about doings that seek to reconcile doing and telling. Treating incivilities as interpreted, this approach combines both field and experimental data (Jucker 2009), and so while the accounts that participants offer may have some flaws (for example, social desirability bias), overall these accounts offer much valid and valuable data.

RIEL researchers gathered accounts of respondents' ‘most recent encounter with a rude stranger.’ Findings echo almost precisely Australian data reported by Smith et al. (2010), showing, for example, that reported incivilities spike at lunchtime, and morning and

evening rush hours, times when people are hurrying, seeking to maximize efficient use of their time. Incivilities are more frequently reported in utilitarian over expressive spaces, that is, in publicly accessible spaces where we are obliged to be in our daily doings (e.g. public transit, grocery stores), rather than in expressive spaces where we are more likely to spend leisure time. This kind of rich data would be difficult to gather by relying on conventional observational methods.

As the accounts reported throughout this article demonstrate, how people talk about those who breach the ritual of civil inattention reference something more than the immediate content of interaction. Accounts of and responses to uncivil encounters—whether *in situ* or *post hoc*—tend to reference the moral order. That is, uncivil encounters provide persons with opportunities to make reference to the moral order, and to assert their own position within it as moral actors.

In the RIEL dataset, negative evaluations of character show up frequently, but even characteriological interpretations tend to suggest that failure to honour the interactional rights of another to civil inattention simultaneously offends something beyond that person. Our participants appeared to treat infractions as offences to the moral order. Indeed, throughout the RIEL dataset, accounts of rude encounters with strangers tend to underscore—rather than undercut—the relationship between everyday encounters gone awry and maintenance of the moral order. Many invoke responsibility to more abstract and deeply moral ideals of responsibility, obligation, worthiness, dignity, egalitarianism, and respect. Even relatively minor acts of ‘interactional vandalism’ (Molotch & Duneier 1999) appear to invoke deep questions of morality and our commitments to one another. Queue-jumpers, it seems, violate something more than the queue.

5. Stranger encounters and/as the problem of moral order

Another account from the RIEL data: as a large crowd filters into a public building, a “girl started opening her arms and pushing through the crowd...pushing everyone out of the way and not even saying excuse me just like walking right through everyone” (RIEL16093)

To review briefly, the most frequent manifestation of politeness and civility in the urban interaction order is civil inattention. Moral demands inhere in encounters and persistent habituated adherence to these demands reproduces a stable moral order that, in turn, provides a general orienting environment for interpreting experience. As Figure 1 (above) demonstrates, interaction ritual provides a structure for enacting everyday morality and so, is the core mechanism for the reproduction of moral order.

Discussing Goffman’s work, Giddens (1987, 124) notes that for strangers “the moment of discarding civil inattention is potentially perilous, since a range of misunderstandings can ensue.... Even the most evanescent of encounters tends to establish something of a bond of moral solidarity between participants.” Clearly, ritual is a solidarizing force. Expectations around how solidarity ought to manifest in ritual interaction, how it is to be appropriately expressed, animate the moral order. It is these manifestations that make

such orders moral. While it can be invoked in interaction, moral order exists as an external structuring force independently of any specific interaction. Simultaneously, moral order is made manifest in the internally coherent organization of interaction. Put differently, moral order has a *sui generis* character, in that it organizes the conduct of members of society, but this organization is not set in stone, it is practically accomplished (Garfinkel 1967) through constant negotiation and repeated ritual renewal (Durkheim 1995). This provides a relatively stable structure for the conduct of everyday activity.

We discern rips and ruptures in the moral order when negotiation fails, when interaction deviates from habitual forms. That said, while moral order is a negotiated order (Maines 1982), that is not all that it is. It is also invoked as motivation and justification, for both affirmation and condemnation of particular kinds of interpersonal conduct. Encounters then not only constitute the moral order, but are also where moral order is called upon. Encounters both make and are made by the moral order. How the moral order figures in the context of “cultural and situational variability” (Okamoto 1999: 51) in interaction remains an open question. Below I use the case of bystander intervention to work through some of the difficulties in theorizing the relationship between incivilities and the moral order.

5.1 Retrospective voicing: where is the moral order if no bystander intervenes?

Last week I was...waiting for the bus...there was an elderly lady waiting to get on...and just as the bus pulls up, opens the door, a guy kinda like ran up, out of the building, where the station is and kinda cut in front of her...he cut in front of her, she didn't say anything, you know elderly lady's polite...everyone in line noticed and you could sense the derision, looking down on him like.....we all waited for her to get on, it was just kinda a silent passing...if he had been more aggressive or if he had actually pushed her then there would have probably been an actual confrontation I imagine (RIEL16015)

Kádár (2017: 2-3) notes that “[m]oral orders are ‘moral’ in the most common sense of the word: if someone violates the moral order, this violation triggers the feeling that something is inappropriate, and this sense of inappropriateness tends to be voiced.” Here the moral nature of the moral order requires explicit expression in the form of voice. In their consideration of Haugh’s (2013) discussion of evaluations of situated expectations and impoliteness, Kádár and Márquez-Reiter (2015) assert that outspoken moral evaluation—voicing—is “triggered” by violations of the moral order. Sociologists, too, connect voicing and intervention. In interaction ritual chain theory, breaches of “positive sentiments of moral solidarity” unleash “righteous anger directed against the culprit” (Collins 2005, 104).

The RIEL data troubles these claims, as both bystander intervention and escalation into ‘righteous anger’ are relatively rare in the sample. Where respondents reported aggression in an interaction, bystander intervention occurred in less than one-third of cases analyzed to date. What we have here then is a puzzle at the pragmatics-sociology

interface. How can we adequately account for why bystander intervention does not seem to happen in the particular context of breaches to the ritual of civil inattention? Further, what does this mean for linking interaction and moral order? Solving this puzzle will require more focused research, but for now, second order accounts from the RIEL dataset provide a potential path for navigating this conceptual impasse.

Talk *about* impoliteness is rife, but in the RIEL dataset at least, ‘voicing’ in the immediate context of the interaction is relatively rare. This does not mean that disapproval is not voiced somewhere. Instead, uncivil encounters provide interactional grist for the *post-encounter* mill of moral talk and projective moral action (Emirbayer and Mische 1998). Thus, Kádár and Márquez-Reiter’s emphasis on the “importance of studying moral principles as they are understood in a lay/philosophical-second order sense, *within* the evaluative action” (2015, 244, emphasis added) can be extended to incorporate evaluative talk *in the wake of* an uncivil encounter. Thus, analysis of “moral evaluation of an ongoing act” (241) can be supplemented by *retrospective voicing*, which I define as *reflective moral evaluation of a completed act*.

In light of the analysis offered above I want to move towards a conclusion by building on the above discussion of the relationship between interaction ritual and moral order to offer a conception of everyday encounters as moral affordances.

6. Outline of a theory of moral affordances: stranger interaction as moral landscape

Advancing a theory of moral affordances means raiding a variety of subdisciplinary closets. Gibson’s (2011) concept of ‘affordances’ is foundational to ecological psychology, positing that elements of our environment suggest, or ‘afford’ particular kind of uses. For example, individual brains do not need to retain knowledge of how to open a door, instead the shape of a door handle affords or lends itself to being turned or pushed down. One could say the same for a chair or table: through our encounter with their materiality they lend themselves to the uses to which we put them. This leads to the claim that affordances exist neither in objects nor in persons, but rather in the interaction between the two. Thus, a range of affordances characterize human-environment interaction. This concept has generated wide-ranging debate within and beyond ecological psychology (Chemero 2003; Michaels 2004; Good 2007), including analysis of the relationship between morality and affordances (Hodges and Baron 1992).

Where ecological psychologists treat affordances as properties of interactions between person and environment, I extend the concept from the material world of inanimate objects to the social world of ritualized interaction. Thus, I treat the ritual dimension of interaction as affording or lending itself to particular forms of conduct. The term ‘moral affordance’ appears in ecological moral realism as the “opportunity for moral behavior” specified as a function of an agent’s “relations between morally relevant abilities and morally relevant situations” (Jayawickreme and Chemero 2008, 122).⁹ While resonating

⁹ Anthropologist Webb Keane (2016, 27) uses the term “moral affordance” to refer to “any aspect of people’s experiences and perceptions that they might draw on in the process of making ethical evaluations and decisions, whether consciously or not”. As with the ecological moral realists, Keane’s is an internalist

with the perspective advanced here, this conception works downwards from the interaction to intra-individual moral reasoning and virtue. Advancing a normative rather than functional (Schmidt 2007) concept of affordance, I treat the encounter as a special kind of affordance whose character is deeply moral. My interest is in moving up and out from the interaction to the moral order. Each encounter affords the opportunity to conduct oneself in line with precedence and culturally appropriate expectations (Schutz 1975) where ritualized interaction both draws on and maintains the moral order.

As an example, a Persian-Canadian woman recounts:

I was at a store, and I was in line with my mom, and there was a lady with her child, and the child was in a carriage cart. As I was standing there I guess I kind of touched the cart by accident, and the lady started yelling at...my mom and me aggressively and calling us names. She said something about, 'Go back to where you're from' – that kind of thing, and she was just very aggressive and rude and the cashier had to intervene and they had to get people to come because she was just, not taking it and was being very aggressive and rude with us (RIEL17046)

In this case of verbal aggression in a supermarket checkout queue, a woman claims to have unintentionally touched the temporary property (shopping cart/trolley) of another customer, leading to a seemingly unprompted use of anti-immigrant language. This leads a third party (a supermarket employee) to intervene. Here, we see that a minor violation of personal space—touching the cart—provokes an extreme verbal response, which in turn leads an employee to intervene as the formal relevant authority tasked with explicitly invoking the moral order. In this case, likely partly due to role obligations, the employee treats the affront as a moral affordance. That said, not all such affordances produce immediate action.

6.1 Moral order as moral landscape: aspirational accounts and projective moral action

The materiality of the affordance in ecological psychology suggests a mode of action in line with physical environment (e.g. stairs suggest that they should be climbed, crawled, jumped, or sat upon). Just as material affordances refer to interaction of person and physical landscape (Rietveld and Kiverstein 2014), moral affordance refers to interactions between persons within the moral order, what we might call *moral landscape*.

The material affordance-physical landscape relationship and the moral affordance-moral landscape relationship are homologously structured. The ritual organization of encounters provides moral affordances, suggesting a palette of available ways to act. The interactional configuration of the uncivil encounter—where an expectancy state is violated, where the offer of indifference is not honoured, where the ritual of civil

perspective, from the viewpoint of the individual, rather than one centred on the *intersubjective* reality of encounter.

inattention is breached—affords possibilities for action to restore/recalibrate the animating principles of the moral order.

As mentioned above, bystander intervention occurs infrequently in the RIEL data. Despite this relative absence, intervention figures very prominently as an aspirational or projective form of agency (Emirbayer and Mische 1998). That is, intervention figures strongly in *talk about* uncivil encounters, with participants discussing at length what they *ought* to have done. Any reflection upon what one should have done is deeply imbricated with the moral: morality is, after all, concerned with oughts.

The ritual dimensions of interaction between strangers in public space provide interactants with moral affordances, that is, opportunities to align themselves with an idealized moral order through projective moral action. Ritualization of interaction provides a structure for demonstrably moral action, or at least for the articulation of what such action ought to look like. So, even if someone does not behave in a way that is moral/just in the interaction, they draw on the moral order to interpret their experience. In this way, the concept of moral affordance gets at the lived experience of interaction and the ideals that permeate the moral order, ideals of what *ought* to be made manifest in interaction rituals. These ideals are drawn upon and grounded by reference to the ritual structure of interaction.

While situational features of interaction structure potential action, everyday responses to and interpretations of incivilities treat them as moral affordances. Bystander intervention aligns an individual actor with an idealized moral order. Accounts permit alignment between experience and idealized lay conceptions of the moral order. These idealized conceptions likely have a deep cultural structure (Alexander 2006) that foregrounds particular ideals as collectively intelligible reference points—a shared scheme of reference (Schutz 1975)—in any given interaction (Enfield 2006; Goodwin 2006; Levinson 2006). Individual actors necessarily operate with the background assumption that these ideals are generally shared, and so these ideals provide reference points for both conduct in interaction and talk about interaction. Thus, while they may also give common ground an abstract form, we cannot assume that these reference points are universal (Ide 1989; Spencer-Oatey and Kádár 2015).

If our analysis is to be trained on connecting interaction ritual and moral order, we cannot treat encounters as flashpoints or lightning rods where the pre-wound spring of an actor's *a priori* fully constituted moral consciousness is released. Such a psychologistic conception of morality cannot account for interactional and situational contingencies. Thus, rather than locate morality exclusively in some particular intra-individual synaptic firing, I posit that the ritual structure of encounters between strangers provides for:

- (1) the collaborative production of situated moral affordances, and
- (2) individual level formulation of projective moral action

It is the ritualized interaction, then, that provides both content and context for projective moral action. In affording opportunities to act morally, ritualized interaction constitutes

the moral order, an order that places particular kinds of obligations on us. In a dual sense then—as both analytic and imperative—we get our moral orders from encounters.

7. Conclusion

In this article I have argued that the everyday ritual of civil inattention that generally pertains between persons unknown to one another plays a key role in the moral order of North American dense urban public spaces, or what I term, the urban interaction order. I showed how moral order is upheld by the persistent enactment of ritualized interaction that provides stability and coherence to encounters where persons may share little else but copresence. Further, I indicated that expectations around the interaction ritual of civil inattention mean that ritual infractions—incivilities—are generally interpreted as profanations of the moral order. Drawing on select cases of persons' accounts of encounters with rude strangers, I suggested that everyday encounters gone awry provide persons with opportunities for demonstrations of moral worth—what I call moral affordances—if not in the immediate scene of interaction, then in *post hoc* reflections on their encounters through what I call retrospective voicing.

The opportunities for future research here are wide ranging. Deeper and more sustained understanding of the ways that uncivil encounters are formed by nested contexts of ever-increasing complexity, from the relatively simple spatio-temporal elements that impact rude encounters, to higher levels of complexity incorporating cultural contexts, will become increasingly necessary as urban public spaces become more dense and heterogenous. This would contribute to deepening our understanding of the importance of context in im/politeness research (Bousfield and Culpeper 2008, 161). Clearly, incivilities highlight the connection between interpersonal conduct and the moral order, but we would do well to further develop an understanding of morality that is contextually sensitive, but not always and inevitably situationally enacted. Rather, interaction's ritual ingredients (Collins 2005) provide tools for sketching the analytic contours of a moral landscape.

Because stranger encounters are imbricated in the maintenance of the moral order, they are not and cannot be treated as morally neutral. Consequently, there is a clear need for focused and sustained research that attends to how and for whom socially ascribed categories figure in the character and course of stranger interactions gone awry. This means divesting ourselves of a desire to find a natural order to interactional conflict between strangers. Variations cross-culturally, across types of public space, and across time of day, for example, suggest that an exclusive focus on universals of human interaction might blinker us to the ways that something so simple as the basic spatio-temporal features of their interactional environment, or as complex as the socially ascribed characteristics of interactants—gender or race, for example—form both encounters and their interpretations.

Clearly there is much for us to learn across a range of disciplines and subfields. Encounters between strangers in particular, might be fruitfully analyzed as social sites where opportunities to demonstrate moral principles are suggested and tested. This is a

project that will continue to unfold as further analysis of the RIEL data proceeds. I hope that the concepts sketched out here help to develop new directions that advance our understanding of the nexus between self, interaction ritual and moral order. With our analytic lens trained on the ever emergent and constant contract between persons and the conditioning force of their immediate social environment, we can weave together a normative and analytic understanding of the centrality of mutual commitment to everyday life amongst physically copresent strangers.

References

- Alexander, Jeffrey. 2006. *The Civil Sphere*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Alexander, Jeffrey, Bernhard Giesen, and Jason L. Mast, eds. 2006. *Social Performance: Symbolic Action, Cultural Pragmatics, and Ritual*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Anderson, Elijah. 2011. *The Cosmopolitan Canopy: Race and Civility in Everyday Life*. New York: Norton.
- Archer, Margaret. 1995. *Realist Social Theory: The Morphogenetic Approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bargiela-Chiappini, Francesca. 2003. "Face and Politeness: New (Insights) for Old (Concepts)." *Journal of Pragmatics* 35 (10–11): 1453–69.
- Blommaert, J. and Piia Varis. 2015. "The Importance of Unimportant Language." *Multilingual Margins* 2(1): 4–9.
- Blumer, Herbert. 1954. "What Is Wrong with Social Theory?" *American Sociological Review* 19 (1): 3–10.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. 2000. *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Bousfield, Derek. 2007. "Beginnings, Middles and Ends: A Biopsy of the Dynamics of Impolite Exchanges." *Journal of Pragmatics* 39 (12): 2185–2216.
- Bousfield, Derek. 2008. *Impoliteness in Interaction*. John Benjamins, Amsterdam/Philadelphia.
- Bousfield, Derek. 2010. "Researching Impoliteness and Rudeness: Issues and Definitions." pp. 101–34 in *Interpersonal Pragmatics, Handbooks of Pragmatics*, S. Graham and M. Locher (eds). Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Bousfield, Derek and Jonathan Culpeper. 2008. "Impoliteness: Eclecticism and Diaspora." *Journal of Politeness Research* 4(2): 161-168.
- Brown, Penelope and Stephen C. Levinson. 1987. *Politeness: Some Universals in Language Usage*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Chemero, Anthony. 2003. "An Outline of a Theory of Affordances." *Ecological Psychology* 15(2):181–95.
- Clark, Herbert. 1992. *Arenas of Language Use*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Collins, Randall. 2005. *Interaction Ritual Chains*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Culpeper, Jonathan. 2011. *Impoliteness: Using Language to Cause Offence*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Culpeper, Jonathan. 2010. "Conventionalised Impoliteness Formulae." *Journal of Pragmatics* 42 (12): 3232–45.

- Culpeper, Jonathan. 1996. "Towards an Anatomy of Impoliteness." *Journal of Pragmatics* 25(3): 349–67.
- Culpeper, Jonathan, and Dániel Kádár, eds. 2010. *Historical (Im)Politeness*. New York: Peter Lang.
- Douglas, Mary. 2005. *Purity and Danger*. New York: Routledge.
- Duneier, Mitchell, and Harvey Molotch. 1999. "Talking City Trouble: Interactional Vandalism, Social Inequality, and the 'Urban Interaction Problem.'" *American Journal of Sociology* 104 (5): 1263–95.
- Durkheim, Émile. 1995. *The Elementary Forms of Religious Life*. New York: Free Press.
- Durkheim, Émile. 1964. *The Division of Labour in Society*. New York: Free Press.
- Emirbayer, Mustafa, and Ann Mische. 1998. "What Is Agency?" *American Journal of Sociology* 103 (4): 962–1023.
- Enfield, N. J. 2013. "Elements of Formulation." in *Embodied Interaction*, Jürgen Streeck, Charles Goodwin, and Curtis LeBaron (eds), 59–66. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Enfield, N.J. 2006. "Social Consequences of Common Ground." In *Roots of Human Sociality: Culture, Cognition and Interaction*, N. J. Enfield and Stephen C. Levinson, (eds). New York: Berg.
- Fine, Gary Alan. 2014. "The Hinge: Civil Society, Group Culture, and the Interaction Order." *Social Psychology Quarterly* 77 (1): 5–26.
- Garcés-Conejos Blitvich, Pilar. 2018. "Globalization, transnational identities, and conflict talk: The superdiversity and complexity of the Latino identity." *Journal of Pragmatics* 134: 120–133.
- Garcés-Conejos Blitvich, Pilar. 2013. "Face, identity and im/politeness. Looking backward, moving forward: From Goffman to practice theory." *Journal of Politeness Research* 9 (1): 1–33.
- Garfinkel, Harold. 1967. *Studies in Ethnomethodology*. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
- Gibson, James. 2011. *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception*. New York: Psychology Press.
- Giddens, Anthony. 1987. *Social Theory and Modern Sociology*. Stanford University Press, Stanford.
- Giddens, Anthony. 1986. *The Constitution of Society: Outline of the Theory of Structuration*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Gilbert, Margaret. 2014. *Joint Commitment: How We Make the Social World*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Goffman, Erving. 1959. *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life*. New York: Anchor Books.
- Goffman, Erving. 1963. *Behavior in Public Places: Notes on the Social Organization of Gatherings*. New York: Free Press.
- Goffman, Erving. 1967. *Interaction Ritual: Essays on Face-to-Face Behavior*. New York: Anchor Books.
- Goffman, Erving. 1971. *Relations in Public: Microstudies of the Public Order*. New York: Harper Row.
- Goffman, Erving and Josef Verhoeven. 1980. "An Interview with Erving Goffman." *Research on Language and Social Interaction* 26(3):317–48.

- Goffman, Erving. 1983a. "The Interaction Order" *American Sociological Review* 48(1):1–17.
- Goffman, Erving. 1983b. "Felicity's Condition." *American Journal of Sociology* 89(1):1–53.
- Good, J. M. M. 2007. "The Affordances for Social Psychology of the Ecological Approach to Social Knowing" *Theory & Psychology*, 17(2), 265–295.
- Goodwin, Charles. 2006. "Human Sociality as Mutual Orientation in a Rich Interactive Environment." In *Roots of Human Sociality: Culture, Cognition and Interaction*, N. J. Enfield and Stephen C. Levinson (eds). New York: Berg.
- Hanks, William. 2006. "Joint Commitment and Common Ground in a Ritual Event." In *Roots of Human Sociality: Culture, Cognition and Interaction*, N. J. Enfield and Stephen C. Levinson (eds.) New York: Berg.
- Haugh, Michael. 2013. "Im/politeness, social practice and the participation order" *Journal of Pragmatics* 58: 52–72.
- Hodges, Bert and Reuben Baron. 1992. "Values as Constraints on Affordances: Perceiving and Acting Properly." *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour* 22(3):263–94.
- Horgan, Mervyn. 2017a. "Interaction, Indifference, Injustice: Elements of a Normative Theory of Urban Solidarity." In *Interrogating the Social: A Critical Sociology for the 21st Century*, edited by Fuyuki Kurasawa, 61–94. New York: Springer.
- Horgan, Mervyn. 2017b. "Mundane Mutualities: Solidarity and Strangership in Everyday Urban Life." In *Place, Diversity and Solidarity*, edited by Stijn Oosterlynck, Nick Schuermans, and Maarten Loopmans, 19–32. New York: Routledge.
- Horgan, Mervyn. 2014. "Durkheim, Development and the Devil: A Cultural Sociology of Community Conflict." *Canadian Journal of Sociology / Cahiers Canadiens de Sociologie* 39 (4): 741–63.
- Horgan, Mervyn. 2012. "Strangers and Strangership." *Journal of Intercultural Studies* 33 (6): 607–22.
- Hutchby, Ian. 2008. "Participants' Orientations to Interruptions, Rudeness and Other Impolite Acts in Talk-in-Interaction." *Journal of Politeness Research*. 4(2): 221–241
- Hutchby, Ian. and M. O'Reilly. 2010. "Children's Participation and the Familial Moral Order in Family Therapy." *Discourse Studies* 12(1): 49–64.
- Ide, Risako. 1996. "'Friendly but Strangers': Self-Disclosure and the Creation of Solidarity at Service Encounters in America." Pp. 143–52 in *SALSA IV: Proceedings of the Fourth Annual Symposium about Language and Society*. Vol. 37. Austin.
- Ide, Sachiko. 1989. "Formal Forms and Discernment: Two Neglected Aspects of Universals of Linguistic Politeness." *Multilingua - Journal of Cross-Cultural and Interlanguage Communication* 8 (2–3): 223–48.
- Jackson, Lucy, Catherine Harris, and Gill Valentine. 2017. "Rethinking Concepts of the Strange and the Stranger." *Social & Cultural Geography* 18 (1): 1–15.
- Jay, Timothy. 2018. "Swearing, Moral Order, and Online Communication." *Journal of Language Aggression and Conflict* 6 (1): 107–26.

- Jayawickreme, Eranda and Anthony Chemero. 2008. "Ecological Moral Realism: An Alternative Theoretical Framework for Studying Moral Psychology." *Review of General Psychology* 12(2):118–26.
- Jayyusi, Lena. 2014. *Categorization and the Moral Order*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis.
- Jucker, Andreas. 2009. "Speech Act Research between Armchair, Field and Laboratory." *Journal of Pragmatics* 41 (8): 1611–35.
- Kádár, Dániel. 2017. *Politeness, Impoliteness and Ritual: Maintaining the Moral Order in Interpersonal Interaction*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kádár, Dániel. 2014. "Heckling — A Mimetic-Interpersonal Perspective." *Journal of Language Aggression and Conflict* 2 (1): 1–35.
- Kádár, Dániel, and Marcel Bax. 2013. "In-Group Ritual and Relational Work." *Journal of Pragmatics* 58: 73–86.
- Kádár, Dániel, and Siân Robinson Davies. 2016. "Ritual, Aggression, and Participatory Ambiguity: A Case Study of Heckling." *Journal of Language Aggression and Conflict* 4 (2): 202–33.
- Kádár, Dániel, and Rosina Márquez-Reiter. 2015. "(Im)Politeness and (Im)Morality: Insights from Intervention." *Journal of Politeness Research* 11 (2): 239–60.
- Kaplan, Danny. 2018. *The Nation and the Promise of Friendship: Building Solidarity through Sociability*. New York: Palgrave.
- Keane, Webb. 2016. *Ethical Life*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Kendrick, Kobin, and Paul Drew. 2016. "Recruitment: Offers, Requests, and the Organization of Assistance in Interaction." *Research on Language and Social Interaction* 49(1): 1–19.
- Levinson, Stephen. 2006. "On the Human 'Interaction Engine.'" In *Roots of Human Sociality: Culture, Cognition and Interaction*, N. J. Enfield and Stephen C. Levinson (eds). New York: Berg.
- Locher, Miriam and Richard Watts. 2005. Politeness Theory and Relational Work. *Journal of Politeness Research*. 1(1): 9-33.
- Lofland, Lyn. 1973. *A World of Strangers: Order and Action in Urban Public Space*. New York: Basic Books.
- Maines, David. 1982. "In Search of Mesostructure: Studies in the Negotiated Order." *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography* 11 (3): 267–79.
- Maynard, Douglas and Don Zimmerman. 1984. "Topical Talk, Ritual and the Social Organization of Relationships." *Social Psychology Quarterly* 47(4):301–16.
- Michaels, Claire. 2003. "Affordances: Four Points of Debate." *Ecological Psychology* 15(2): 135–48.
- Ohashi, Jun and Wei-Lin Melody Chang. 2017. "(Im)Politeness and Relationality." Pp. 257–85 in *The Palgrave Handbook of Linguistic (Im)politeness*, J. Culpeper, M. Haugh, and D. Z. Kádár (eds). London: Palgrave.
- Okamoto, Shigeko. 1999. "Situating Politeness: Manipulating Honorific and Non-Honorific Expressions in Japanese Conversations." *Pragmatics* 9(1): 51–74.
- Parvaresh, Vahid, and Tahmineh Tayebi. 2018. "Impoliteness, Aggression and the Moral Order." *Journal of Pragmatics* 132 (July): 91–107.
- Phillips, Tim and Philip Smith. 2003. "Everyday Incivility: Towards a Benchmark." *The Sociological Review* 51(1):85–108.

- Rawls, Anne Warfield. 2010. "Social Order as Moral Order." In *Handbook of the Sociology of Morality*, Steven Hitlin & Stephen Vaisey (eds), 95–121. New York: Springer.
- Rawls, Anne Warfield. 1990. "Emergent Sociality: A Dialectic of Commitment and Order." *Symbolic Interaction* 13 (1): 63–82.
- Rietveld, Erik and Julian Kiverstein. 2014. "A Rich Landscape of Affordances." *Ecological Psychology* 26(4): 325–52.
- Schegloff, Emanuel. 1992. "Repair After Next Turn: The Last Structurally Provided Defense of Intersubjectivity in Conversation." *American Journal of Sociology* 97 (5): 1295–1345.
- Schmidt, R. C. 2007. "Scaffolds for Social Meaning." *Ecological Psychology* 19 (2): 137–51.
- Schutz, Alfred. 1975. *On Phenomenology and Social Relations*. Helmut Wagner, ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Schwartz, Barry. 1975. *Queuing and Waiting: Studies in the Social Organization of Access and Delay*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Scott, Marvin B. and Stanford M. Lyman. 1968. "Accounts." *American Sociological Review* 33(1):46–62.
- Simmel, Georg. 1971. *On Individuality and Social Forms*. D. Levine, ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Smith, Philip and Ryan D. King. 2013. "From Road Rage to Everyday Automotive Incivility: A Routine Activities Approach to Low-Level Deviance." *The Sociological Quarterly* 54(3):476–500.
- Smith, Philip, Timothy L. Phillips, and Ryan D. King. 2010. *Incivility: The Rude Stranger in Everyday Life*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Spencer-Oatey, Helen, and Dániel Z. Kádár. 2015. "The Bases of (Im)Politeness Evaluations: Culture, the Moral Order and the East–West Debate." *East Asian Pragmatics* 1 (1): 73–106.
- Stalnaker, Robert. 2002. "Common Ground." *Linguistics and Philosophy* 25 (5–6): 701–21.
- Turner, R. 1970. "Words, Utterances, Activities." In *Understanding Everyday Life*. Jack Douglas, ed. Chicago: Aldine.
- Turner, Victor W. 1995. *The Ritual Process: Structure and Anti-Structure*. New York: Aldine de Gruyter.
- Valentine, G. 2008. "Living with Difference: Reflections on Geographies of Encounter." *Progress in Human Geography* 32 (3): 323–37.
- Walum, L. 1974. "The Changing Door Ceremony: Notes on the Operation of Sex Roles in Everyday Life." *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography* 2 (4): 506–15.
- Wuthnow, Robert. 1989. *Meaning and Moral Order*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

